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Perception Of Women On Potash Consumption In Yobe State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the perception of women on potash consumption in Yobe State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three (3) research questions. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for this study was 12,420 which comprised of 7081 Pregnant Women and 5339 Lactating Mothers. Sample for this study was 714 consisting of 357 pregnant women and 357 lactating mothers obtained using standard statistical determinant table by Krejcie and Morgan. Multi Staged sampling and convenience sampling techniques were the sampling techniques utilized by the study. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability coefficient of 0.97 was obtained. Data was analyzed using percentage, mean and standard deviation. Findings revealed that all the respondents consume potash. Findings revealed that the ways potash can be consumed included for tenderizing foods that take long time to cook, added to thicken porridge and gruel, used as food preservative and for seasoning foods. Findings indicated that the ways of creating awareness of potash consumption among women in Yobe State included through workshop, seminar, newspaper, fliers, radio announcements, journal articles and social media platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook. Among recommendations made was that various mass media should be utilized in creating awareness of the effect of potash consumption on health of women. Also, different health care providers can be utilized in disseminating awareness on potash consumption to pregnant women and lactating mothers.

Keywords: Consumption, Lactating, Mothers, Pregnant Women, Potash

INTRODUCTION

Nutrients are chemical substances found in food. They provide nourishment for organisms. Nutrients entail all substances that plants or animals including humans need for optimal growth and development. Eze and Njoku (2022) noted that nutrients are chemical substances obtained from food and used in the body to provide energy, structural materials and regulating agents to support growth, maintain and repair of body tissues. The study of food nutrients and how the body absorbs the nutrients in foods for nourishment is known as nutrition. Nutrition is the science that interprets the interaction of nutrients and other substances in food in relation to maintenance, growth, reproduction and health of an organism. Nutrition as used in the study involves the selection of foods, preparation

of foods, and their ingestion to be assimilated by the body. Nutrition explores individual's choice of foods and the type of diet they eat. According to Khanna and Tosh (2014), nutrition is the science that study nutrients and other substances in foods and in the body and the way those nutrients relate to health and disease. Nutrition focuses on two functions in the body which are having good or standard diet which can nourish the body and poor diet which can lead to poor health. Nwaeze (2024) reported that for optimal mental, psychological and physical well-being, individuals need adequate nutrition.

Adequate nutrition entails taking of diet that contains food nutrients in the right proportion. McClaire, Stephen, Machanik, Jeffery, Bistran, Graham, Hagazo, Jessen, Kushner and Merritt (2016) reported that adequate nutrition is a diet that provides all the essential nutrients and calories needed to maintain good health and acceptable body weight. An adequate diet provides essential nutrients needed to keep an individual healthy. Essential nutrients include carbohydrates, proteins, fats and oils, minerals, vitamins and water. Vitamins and minerals are micronutrients while carbohydrates, fats and proteins are macronutrients. Macronutrients are required by the body in large amounts for provision of calories or energy as well as maintenance of body structures. The macronutrients provide structural material (amino acids from which proteins are built, and lipids from which cell membranes and some signaling molecules are built) and energy (McClaire, et. al., 2016).

On the other hand, nutrients needed in small amounts by the body are called micronutrients. Micronutrients consist of vitamins and minerals. Bentoun and Jaris (2012) noted that vitamins are essential in small quantities to regulate body processes, maintain the body, and enhance growth and reproduction. Unlike other nutrients, vitamins are susceptible to being destroyed by heat, light, and other agents. Minerals are also required by the body in small amounts. Mineral is an element that originates in the Earth and always retains its chemical identity. Nwangwu (2024) reported that minerals occur as inorganic crystalline salts. Once minerals enter the body, they remain there until excreted. They cannot be changed into anything else. Minerals cannot be destroyed by heat, air, light or other agents. Minerals are divided into two categories: macro-minerals and trace minerals/trace elements. As implied by their name, macro-minerals are required by the body in larger quantities (more than 100 mg daily) than trace elements. The trace minerals are so named because they are needed in relatively small amounts in the body.

The trace mineral contents of foods depend on soil and water composition and on how foods are processed. Sudi, Maina, Bello, Hauwa and Modibbo (2015) noted that the trace minerals are iron, manganese, copper, iodine, cobalt, zinc, fluoride and selenium while the macro-minerals are calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, chloride, sulphur and potassium. Each mineral performs specific function in the body, which makes each unique and irreplaceable. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2014) summarized the functions of minerals in the body to include Calcium (Ca) for bones and teeth; Magnesium (Mg) for bones and energy metabolism; Phosphorus (P) for bones, teeth, energy metabolism and for genes support; Zinc (Zn) for gene expression and proper immune function; and Potassium (K) for nerve and muscle activity as well as blood pressure. The study focused on potassium as a mineral excessively consumed in Yobe State.

The word "potassium" is derived from potash. Potash contains potassium in water soluble form. In Yobe State in Northern Nigeria, there is an abundant availability of geological mineral known as potash. Ibeme (2015) described potash as "kanwa" (or *akanwu*) as the local Nigerian name for crystal soda. Potash is a crystallised hydrous carbonate of sodium. Oyeleke (2018) described potash as a type of various mined and manufactured salts that contain potassium in water-soluble form. Potash ores are typically rich in potassium chloride (KCl), sodium chloride (NaCl) and other salts and clays (Bankole, Njokere, Ajibade, Igunbor and Ejoka, 2015). Ochei, Omeh, Obeagu and Obarezi (2014) stated that potash refers to potassium compounds and potassium-bearing materials and the most common being potassium chloride (KCl). Bankole, et. al. (2015) mentioned that potash has different varieties such as Crystal Soda carbonate $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ called Trona or as bicarbonate $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{NaHCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ called Natron or as powdery anhydrous carbonate of sodium Na_2CO_3 , or as Crystal Potash (granular potash, crystallised hydrous carbonate of potassium $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), or as powdery anhydrous pearl ash K_2CO_3 .

Powdery anhydrous pearl ash is organic potash locally produced from burnt wood and plant ashes, while mineral potash is industrially produced from solvay process which chemically treats common salt solution with ammonia and carbon dioxide, (Ibeme (2015). Potash is usually alkaline (soapy)

when dissolved in water. Potash is used medically for treating some sorts of ailments in Northern Nigeria. McClare *et. al.* (2016) reported that potash can be administered as medicine for treating ailments such as gastro intestinal problem, skin infection, respiratory problem, reproductive problem, and endocrine disturbances. The excessive consumption of potash may lead to its accumulation that could cause severe and irreparable damage to the kidney and disrupt normal body functions which may eventually lead to loss of life (Bankole, *et. al.* 2015). When taken in excess, the sodium in potash accumulates in the blood causing raised blood pressure. Excessive consumption of potash can be attributed to dietary habits of the people.

Dietary habits are the habitual decisions of individuals or culture made where there is a choice of what foods to eat. People eat according to learned behaviours regarding acceptable food, etiquette, meal and snack patterns, food combinations, and portion sizes. Kiomoff (2016) stated that individual, social, cultural, religious, economic, environmental, and political factors all influence people's dietary habits. People from different cultural background have certain beliefs regarding some food. Availability of potash in large quantities in the study area could be the cultural and environmental factor influencing its consumption.

Potash is a natural mineral deposit found in abundant quantities in Yobe State. The researcher observed that in Yobe State, different categories of women especially pregnant women and lactating mothers consume potash excessively for various reasons. A pregnant woman is one who is expectant. Pregnancy can be described as a period of conception. Eze and Njoku (2022) noted that nutrition in pregnancy refers to nutrient intakes before, during and after pregnancy. Adequate nutrition is important in pregnancy as it determines optimum growth and development of the fetus as well as favourable pregnancy outcomes. On the other hand, A lactating mother is one who is breast feeding a baby. Lactation is a process by which female mammals breastfed their young. A lactating mother needs extra good quality nutrients to meet her nutrient needs and that of her baby. This is because the baby gets nutritional needs through what the mother eat as breast milk. This therefore implies that pregnant mother and lactating mothers need sufficient quantities of calories and all nutrients since they are feeding for themselves and the baby.

A cursory observation of the dietary pattern in Yobe State indicates that the pregnant women and lactating mothers add potash to almost all the foods cooked. This is worrisome as the women see nothing wrong in their dietary behaviour. Potash consumption among women in Yobe State is a cultural dietary pattern which will likely have profound effects on the quality of their health. Egharevba, Ibrahim, Kassam, and Kunle (2015), reported that there is a strong positive relationship between people's cultural beliefs, lifestyle practices and health. However, creating awareness on nutrition would help people change or modify their dietary practices. Nutrition awareness entails enlightening people on healthy eating through various media such as newsletters, radio broadcast, television broadcast, handbills, billboards, workshops, seminars and community extension programmes. However, available literature showed that there is dearth information on the perception of women on potash composition in Yobe State.

Statement of the Problem

High consumption rate of a particular food such as potash among individuals in urban and rural areas in Yobe State is a dietary habit that has important implications for public health. Potash is consumed in different forms, either eaten raw or added to foods as additive by the community dwellers. Inadequate awareness and knowledge of available foods and their nutritional values can be attributed to inappropriate dietary practices which in the long run cause nutrition related diseases. The community dwellers might be ignorant of the hazardous effects of potash consumption on their health. United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) (2012) stated that individuals' awareness or tacit assumptions about food are key determinants of food choices and dietary habits. In Yobe State, the women use potash as a food additive for food preservation, thickener, emulsifier, tenderizer and food flavouring.

In Yobe state, high consumption of potash could lead to detrimental effects on health. For instance, it would lead to different injurious and terminal illness with unknown cause and devastating effects in such a way that one needs to be careful of what one consumes (Nwaeze, 2024). However, different categories of the people in the area of study consumed potash in various forms and for different reasons. Without knowing the consequences that consuming a food nutrient excessively would likely

lead to detrimental effects on the body. This study therefore determined the perception of women on potash consumption in Yobe State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to determine the perception of women on potash consumption in Yobe State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study:

1. Determined the proportion of potash users among pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State,
2. Identified the ways potash is consumed by pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State,
3. Determined the ways of creating awareness of potash usage among pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State,

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What proportion of pregnant women and lactating mothers consume potash in Yobe State?
2. What are the ways of potash consumption by pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State?
3. What are the ways of creating awareness of Potash usage among pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State?

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study: The study adopted descriptive survey design. Descriptive survey is a type of study which aims at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population under study (Uzoagulu, 2011). Descriptive survey was considered appropriate for this study because the opinions of women on types of potash consumed, different ways potash was consumed, uses of potash, reasons for using potash and ways of creating awareness of potash consumption was sought, analysed and interpreted.

Area of the Study: The study was carried out in Yobe State, Nigeria. Yobe State is located in North East Nigeria. The capital of Yobe State is Damaturu. The State borders the Republic of Niger to the north and the Nigerian States of Borno to the east, Gombe to the southwest, Bauchi to the west and Jigawa to the northwest. The state has large solid mineral deposits of potash (*Kaun*) found in different varieties. The mineral deposits of potash made the state a potential mining area which has led to increased economic benefits.

Population for the Study: The population for this study comprised of 12,420 women in Yobe State. The population was made up of the following two groups comprising: Pregnant Women (7081) and Lactating Mothers (5339). (Source: Yobe State Hospital Management Board, 2019). These two groups of women were chosen as population for the study because observation shows that they are the groups that mostly consume potash excessively for various reasons.

Sample and Sampling Techniques: Sample for this study was 714. This was drawn from the two groups comprising: 357 pregnant women and 357 lactating mothers. The study adopted a standard statistical determinant table by Krejcie and Morgan, (1970) cited in Emaikwu (2008) to obtain the sample size. According to Emaikwu (2008), for a study of known population, the standard determinant table for sample size can be used. From the standard statistical determinant table, a sample of 357 was drawn from 7081 Pregnant Women and 357 from 5359 Lactating Mothers.

Two sampling techniques were utilized to draw the samples. The sampling techniques included multi-stage sampling and convenience sampling. In stage 1 of the multi staged sampling technique, Yobe State was divided into 3 using the senatorial zones. This helped to categorize the pregnant women and lactating mothers in the state into three. The three senatorial zones was: Yobe East, Yobe North and Yobe South. In stage 2 of the multi staged sampling technique, two senatorial zones were chosen from the three zones. The zones chosen are Yobe East (Damaturu) and Yobe North (Gashua). The reason for selecting these two senatorial zones is because they are more populated with large number of pregnant women and lactating mothers who patronize the general hospitals in the zones. In stage 3 of the multistage sampling technique, 357 pregnant women and 357 lactating mothers was selected.

From the 357 pregnant women, 179 was selected from Gashua General Hospital while 178 was selected from the general hospital in Damaturu. On the other hand, from the 357 lactating mothers, 179 was chosen from Gashua General Hospital while 178 was selected from the general hospital in Damaturu. Purposive sampling technique was used to select pregnant women, lactating mothers and elderly that attend general hospitals and health centers in Yobe State. Convenience sampling technique was also used to select the pregnant women and lactating mothers that visit the general hospital.

Instrument for Data Collection: Questionnaire on Potash Consumption was used for data collection. The questionnaire was titled Questionnaire on Potash Consumption (QPC). The questionnaire was used to gather information concerning the types of potash consumed by the women, different ways potash is consumed, the reasons for potash consumption as well as the ways of creating awareness for the pregnant women and lactating mothers. The questionnaire was constructed based on the purposes of the study and was also developed through extensive literature reviewed on types of potash consumed by women, different ways potash is consumed, the reasons for potash consumption, as well as ways of creating awareness on potash consumption.

The first section (Section A) of the questionnaire contained demographic information of the respondents. This included: age, religion, Local Government Area, name of General Hospital and educational qualification. Section B determined the proportion and percentage of pregnant women and lactating mothers who consume potash. The proportion that consumes potash were asked to respond to the second part of the section that contained 21 items on the different ways potash is consumed by the pregnant women and lactating mothers. Each item had four options, which the respondents indicated their responses. The responses was based on a four point rating scale of: Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1. Section E contained 19 items on the ways of creating nutrition awareness to the pregnant women and lactating mothers on potash consumption. Each item had four options, which the respondents indicated their responses. The responses were based on a four-point scale of: Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1.

Validation of Instrument: The questionnaire on potash consumption was subjected to face validation by three experts. One of the experts was a Lecturer from Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, Faculty of Vocational Technical Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka; one was a Lecturer from Home Economics Department, Federal University Gashua Yobe State and senior nurse from Yobe State General Hospital. The experts assessed the clarity, relevance, appropriateness of the instruments for data collection based on the purpose of the study and research questions. The researcher integrated their suggestions, modifications and corrections in the final copies of the instruments.

Reliability of Instrument: The reliability of the instrument was done using cronbach alpha method. The validated instrument was trial tested on 20 women in Jigawa State. Jigawa State shares common boundary with Yobe State hence they have similar characteristics of potash consumption. Twenty copies of the instrument was administered to the women in Jigawa State. After two weeks, the same women was given the same instruments to respond to. Thereafter, the cronbach alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument and it yielded a reliability was 0.97 implying that the instrument was reliable for use.

Method of Data Collection: Data was collected through the use of the questionnaire. The researcher obtained written approval from Yobe State Hospital Management Board. This enabled the researcher gain access to the respondents within the hospital premises. Informed consent was sought from the pregnant women and lactating mothers. This enabled them give willingness to participate in the study. The researcher also distributed the questionnaire through the help of three research assistants. The research assistants were briefed on the nature of the study. They also assisted the respondents in filling the questionnaire especially the lactating mothers who might be busy with their baby. Out of the 714 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 699 were retrieved indicating 97% return rate.

Method of Data Analysis: Data obtained was analyzed using percentage, mean and standard deviation. All data collected were analysed using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. For the decision rule, the real limits of the numbers of the respondents' mode were used to categorise the mean responses of the respondents. Any mean ratings with 2.50 or above were regarded

as agreed upon and accepted while mean ratings that were less than 2.5 were regarded as disagreed upon and rejected.

RESULTS

Demographic Information of Respondents

1. Age of the respondents showed that 46 (6%) were within ages 12 - 19 yrs; 289 (41%) were within ages 20- 29 yrs; 257 (36%) were within ages 30 - 39 yrs; 109 (15%) were within ages 40 -49 yrs; 13 (2%) were within ages 50 - 59 yrs while none was above 60 yrs.
2. Educational qualification of the respondents indicated that 102 (14%) had no formal education; 193 (28%) had primary school certificate; 159 (22%) had senior secondary school certificate (SSCE); 87 (12%) had OND or its equivalent; 144 (20%) had HND, BSc., B.A, B.Ed and its equivalent while 29 (4%) had Adult Education and literacy programme.
3. Religion of the respondents showed that 45 (7%) were christians while 669 (93%) were muslims.

Table 1: Percentage of the Proportion of Respondents on Potash Consumption

S/N	Respondent	Number	Percentage
1.	Pregnant Women	357	50%
2.	Lactating Mother	357	50%
	Total	714	100%

Table 1 contains percentage of the proportion of respondents that consume potash. From the analysis, 357 (50%) of pregnant women consume potash while 357 (50%) of lactating mothers also consume potash. This indicated that all the respondents consume potash.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on Ways of Potash Consumption by Pregnant Women and Lactating Mothers in Yobe State

S/N	Ways Potash is Consumed by the Women	X	SD	Decision
1.	Used for tenderizing foods that take long time to cook	3.99	0.11	Agreed
2.	Added to thicken porridge and gruel	3.96	0.25	Agreed
3.	Used to enhance food palatability	3.88	0.39	Agreed
4.	To enhance texture of food	3.95	0.26	Agreed
5.	Used as a food preservative	3.87	0.39	Agreed
6.	For seasoning foods	3.98	0.12	Agreed
7.	For emulsifying oils in foods	3.92	0.35	Agreed
8.	For smoothening gruel like kunu and pap	3.73	0.64	Agreed
9.	To reduce bitter taste of some vegetables like bitter leaf,	3.88	0.39	Agreed
10.	Cooking green vegetables in order to help retain colour	3.75	0.39	Agreed
11.	As a laxative for purging	3.86	0.46	Agreed
12.	For relieving constipation	3.92	0.57	Agreed
13.	As a flavouring for enhancing aroma of food	3.84	0.48	Agreed
14.	For enhancing taste of food	3.87	0.52	Agreed
15.	For removing bitter taste in pregnant women mouth	3.44	0.77	Agreed
16.	As a refreshing drink for pregnant women	3.15	0.95	Agreed
17.	As a nourishing drink for boosting breast milk	3.16	0.98	Agreed
18.	As a food sweetener	3.38	0.84	Agreed
19.	As a nourishing drink for increasing nutrients in breast milk	3.74	0.64	Agreed
20.	Ground and used as snuff	3.82	0.49	Agreed
21.	Added to food to make the food more digestible	3.77	0.64	Agreed

Key: X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Respondents = 714 (357 Pregnant women and 357 Lactating mothers).

Table 2 contains the mean and standard deviation responses on ways potash is consumed by the pregnant women and lactating mothers. 21 items were used to elicit responses on 4-point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Result from the table showed that all of the 21 items were agreed upon as ways potash is consumed by pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State with mean responses ranging from 3.15 to 3.99.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on Ways of Creating Awareness of Potash Usage among Pregnant Women and Lactating Mothers in Yobe State

S/N	Ways of Creating Awareness of Potash Usage	X	SD	Decision
1.	Workshop	3.94	0.29	Agreed
2.	Seminar	3.84	0.40	Agreed
3.	Nutrition and Health talks	3.89	0.37	Agreed
4.	Newspaper	3.39	0.83	Agreed
5.	Fliers	3.22	0.68	Agreed
6.	Billboards	3.33	0.60	Agreed
7.	Flex displays	3.51	0.74	Agreed
8.	Radio Announcements	3.90	0.37	Agreed
9.	Television shows	3.03	0.84	Agreed
10.	Journal Articles	3.17	0.77	Agreed
11.	Local community leaders	3.84	0.44	Agreed
12.	Flip charts	3.06	1.01	Agreed
13.	Internet	3.47	0.56	Agreed
14.	Extension services	3.39	0.55	Agreed
15.	Town criers	2.23	1.23	Disagreed
16.	Women meetings	3.67	0.53	Agreed
17.	Age group gathering	3.49	0.54	Agreed
18.	House-to- house counselling	3.94	0.32	Agreed
19.	Social media platforms such as Whatsapp and Facebook	3.89	0.34	Agreed

Key: X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Respondents = 714 (357 Pregnant women and 357 Lactating mothers)

Table 3 contains the mean and standard deviation responses on ways of creating awareness of potash usage by the pregnant women and lactating mothers. 19 items were used to elicit responses on 4-point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Result from the table showed that 18 items were agreed upon as ways of creating awareness of potash usage by pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State with mean responses ranging from 3.03 to 3.94 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50. However, the respondents disagreed with 1 item (town criers with mean = 2.23) as a way of creating awareness of potash consumption. On the other hand, standard deviation responses ranged from 0.29 to 1.23 indicating that the mean responses were not far from each other.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings showed that all the respondents consume potash. In line with the findings, Rabiun and Abubakar (2020) reported that traditionally in Northern Nigeria, people of all ages consume different types of potash for various reasons. Also, in line with the finding, Bedan, Nicholas and Martha (2017) noted that people consume potash because it is believed to have medicinal values.

Findings indicated that the ways potash is consumed by the pregnant women and lactating mothers included being used for smoothening gruel like kunu and pap, used to reduce bitter taste of some vegetables like bitter leaf, for cooking green vegetable in order to help retain their colour, used as a laxative for purging, for relieving constipation, used as flavouring for food, for enhancing taste of food, for removing bitter taste in the mouth of pregnant women, used as a refreshing drink for pregnant women, as a nourishing drink for boosting breast milk, as food sweetener, as nourishing drink for increasing nutrients in breast milk, ground and used as snuff and added to food to make the food more digestible. In agreement with the findings, Alasiru, Mohammed and Abdulahi (2011) reported that potash is used medically for treating some sorts of ailments in Northern Nigeria. McClare *et. al.* (2016) reported that potash can be administered as medicine for treating ailments such as gastro intestinal problem, skin infection, respiratory problem, reproductive problem, and endocrine disturbances. Chinedum, Njideka, Ifeanyi & Ndubuisi, (2015) stated that potash mixed in water is administered to women immediately after child birth as a medicine to increase lactation. To further

buttress the findings, Muhammad, Said, Bilbis, Onu, Isezuo, and Sahabi (2014) reported that potash can be used in various mixtures to treat dandruff, problems related to pregnancy, eye disorders, infertility, and as an ingredient in herbal concoctions.

Findings also revealed that potash can be used for tenderizing foods that take long time to cook; added to thicken porridge and gruel, used to enhance food palatability; used to enhance texture of food, used as food preservative, for seasoning foods and for emulsifying oils in foods. In agreement with these findings, Mohammed *et. al.* (2014) stated that potash is used as food additive as preservative, thickener, emulsifier, stabilizer, texturizer, tenderizing meat, beans and other foods that take long time to become soft. Kutshik, Idogun, Ujah, and Gotom, (2018) opined that cowpea which is noted for its prolonged cooking time of 40-65 minutes was reduced to 10-15 minutes when cooked with a high concentration of potash (0.1 – 0.5%). Also, in line with the findings, Bankole, *et. al.* (2015) reported that potash can be used to increase the green colour and texture of vegetables as well as reduce the cooking time of legumes. Also, Rabiun and Malami (2019) stated that potash can be used for the treatment of cough, toothache relief, fungicidal and as food preservative.

Findings revealed the ways of creating awareness of potash usage by the pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State included: workshop, seminar, nutrition and health talks, newspaper, fliers, billboards, flex displays, radio announcements, television shows, journal articles, community leaders, flip charts, internet, extension services, women meetings, age group gathering, house-to-house counselling and social media platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook. In agreement with the findings, WHO (2014) recommends mass media campaigns as one of best methods of creating nutrition awareness towards prevention and control of diseases. (Nwaeze, 2024) advocated that mass media can be utilized through a variety of channels including: health and education-related settings; public relations events, such as talks, demonstrations and tours, social media, mass communication approaches, nutrition communication and individual counselling to educate people on nutrition awareness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that all the respondents consume potash. The findings revealed several ways potash can be consumed by pregnant women and lactating mothers in Yobe State. Findings revealed that the ways of creating awareness of potash consumption among women in Yobe State included workshop, seminar, nutrition and health talks, newspaper, fliers, billboards, flex displays, radio announcements, television shows, journal articles, community leaders, flip charts, internet, extension services, women meetings, age group gathering, house-to-house counselling and social media platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Various mass media should be utilized in creating awareness of the effect of potash consumption on health of women.
2. Pregnant women should be discouraged from consuming potash through mass media.
3. Awareness should be created to lactating mothers on the harmful effects of consuming potash.
4. Different health care providers can be utilized in disseminating awareness on potash consumption to pregnant women and lactating mothers.

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